

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 147

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 147

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 147:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! For ^ait is good to sing praises to our God; For ³it is pleasant <i>and</i> praise is ^bbecoming. ² The LORD ^abuilds up Jerusalem; He ^bgathers the outcasts of Israel. ³ He heals the ^abrokenhearted And ^bbinds up their ¹wounds. ⁴ He ^acounts the number of the stars; He ^{1b}gives names to all of them. ⁵ ^aGreat is our Lord and abundant in strength; His ^bunderstanding is ¹infinite. ⁶ The LORD ^{1a}supports the afflicted; He brings down the wicked to the ground.</p>	<p>Psa. 147:1 תִּלְלוּ יְהוָה כִּי־טוֹב זְמִירָה אֲלֹהֵינוּ כִּי־נָעִים נֶאֱמָרָה תְהַלְלָהּ :² בּוֹנֵה יְרוּשָׁלַם יְהוָה נְדַחֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל יַכְנִס :³ הַרְפֵּא לְשִׁבְרֵי לֵב וּמְחַיֵּשׁ לְעֵצְבוֹתָם :⁴ מוֹנֵה מִסְפָּר לְכּוֹכְבִים לְכֹלָם שְׁמוֹת יִקְרָא :⁵ גָּדוֹל אֲדוֹנֵינוּ וְרַב־כֹּחַ לְתַבוּנָתוֹ אֵין מִסְפָּר :⁶ מְעוֹדֵד עֲנָוִים יְהוָה מִשְׁפִּיל רְשָׁעִים עַד־יֶאֱרֶץ :⁷ עָנּוּ לִיהוָה בְּתוֹדָה וּמְרוֹ לְאֱלֹהֵינוּ בְּכִנּוֹר :⁸ הַמְכֹסֶה שָׁמַיִם אֲבַעְבִּים הַמְכִין לְאֶרֶץ מָטָר הַמַּצְמִיחַ הָרִים חֲצִיר :⁹ נוֹתֵן לְבַהֲמָה לְחֵמָה לְבִנְי עֹרֵב אֲשֶׁר יִקְרָאוּ :¹⁰ לֹא בְגִבוּרַת הַסּוּס יִחַפֵּץ לֹא־בְשׁוֹקֵי הָאִישׁ יִרְצֶה :¹¹ רוּצֶה יְהוָה אֶת־יִרְאָיו אֶת־הַמִּיַחֲלִים לְחַסְדּוֹ :¹² שִׁבְחֵי יְרוּשָׁלַם אֶת־יְהוָה הַלְלֵי אֱלֹהֵיךָ צִיּוֹן :¹³ כִּי־חִזַּק בְּרִיתֵי שְׁעָרֶיךָ בִּרְךְ בְּנִיךְ בְּקִרְבֶּךָ :¹⁴ תִּשְׁם־ גְּבוּלֶךָ שָׁלוֹם חֵלֶב חֲטָיִם יִשְׂבִיעֶךָ :¹⁵ הַשְׁלַח אֲמַרְתוּ אֶרֶץ עַד־מְהֵרָה יִרוּץ דְּבָרוֹ :¹⁶ תִּנְתֵּן שִׁלְג כַּצְמֹר כְּפֹר כְּאֶפֶר יִפּוֹר :¹⁷ מִשְׁלֵיךְ</p>
<p>Psa. 147:7 ^aSing to the LORD with thanksgiving; Sing praises to our God on the lyre, ⁸ Who ^acovers the heavens with clouds, Who ^bprovides rain for the earth, Who ^cmakes grass to ¹grow on the mountains. ⁹ He ^agives to the beast its food, <i>And</i> to the ^byoung ravens which cry. ¹⁰ He does not delight in the strength of the ^ahorse;</p>	

He ^bdoes not take pleasure in the legs of a man.

¹¹ The LORD ^afavours those who fear Him,

^bThose who wait for His lovingkindness.

Psa. 147:12 Praise the LORD, O Jerusalem!

Praise your God, O Zion!

¹³ For He has strengthened the ^abars of your gates;

He has ^bblessed your sons within you.

¹⁴ He ^amakes ¹peace in your borders; He ^bsatisfies you with ^cthe ²finest of the wheat.

¹⁵ He sends forth His ^acommand to the earth;

His ^bword runs very swiftly.

¹⁶ He gives ^asnow like wool; He scatters the ^bfrost like ashes.

¹⁷ He casts forth His ^aice as fragments;

Who can stand before His ^bcold?

¹⁸ He ^asends forth His word and melts them;

He ^bcauses His wind to blow and the waters to flow.

¹⁹ He ^adeclares His words to Jacob, His ^bstatutes and His ordinances to Israel.

²⁰ He ^ahas not dealt thus with any nation;

And as for His ordinances, they have ^bnot known them.

¹Praise ²the LORD!

קָרָתוֹ כְּבִתִּים לְפָנַי קָרָתוֹ מִי
יַעֲמֹד : 18 יִשְׁלַח דְּבָרוֹ וַיִּמָּסֶם יִשָּׁב
רֹאֲחוֹ יִזְלוּ-מֵיָם : 19 מִגִּיד דְּבָרוֹ
[דְּבָרָיו] לִיעֲקֹב חֲקִיו וַיִּמְשָׁפְטֵיו
לְיִשְׂרָאֵל : 20 לֹא עָשָׂה כֵן אֶלְכָל-
גֹּי וַיִּמְשָׁפְטֵים בְּלִי-יָדָעוֹם הַלְלוּ-
יְהוָה :

References

Psalm 147:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

³Or *He is gracious*

^aPs 92:1; 135:3

^bPs 33:1

Psalm 147:2

^aPs 51:18; 102:16

^bDeut 30:3; Ps 106:47; Is 11:12; 56:8; Ezek 39:28

Psalm 147:3

¹Lit *sorrows*

^aPs 34:18; 51:17; Is 61:1

^bJob 5:18; Is 30:26; Ezek 34:16

Psalm 147:4

¹Or *calls them all by their names*

^aGen 15:5

^bIs 40:26

Psalm 147:5

¹Lit *innumerable*

^aPs 48:1; 145:3

^bIs 40:28

Psalm 147:6

¹Or *relieves*

^aPs 37:24; 146:8, 9

Psalm 147:7

^aPs 33:2; 95:1, 2

Psalm 147:8

¹Lit *spring forth*

^aJob 26:8

^bJob 5:10; 38:26; Ps 104:13

Job 38:27; Ps 104:14

Psalm 147:9

^aPs 104:27, 28; 145:15

^bJob 38:41; Matt 6:26

Psalm 147:10

^aPs 33:17

^{b1} Sam 16:7

Psalm 147:11

^aPs 149:4

^bPs 33:18

Psalm 147:13

^aNeh 3:3; 7:3

^bPs 37:26

Psalm 147:14

¹Lit *your borders peace*

²Lit *fat*

^aPs 29:11; Is 54:13; 60:17, 18

^bPs 132:15

^cDeut 32:14; Ps 81:16

Psalm 147:15

^aJob 37:12; Ps 148:5

^bPs 104:4

Psalm 147:16

^aJob 37:6; Ps 148:8

^bJob 38:29

Psalm 147:17

^aJob 37:10

^bJob 37:9

Psalm 147:18

^aPs 33:9; 107:20; 147:15

^bPs 107:25

Psalm 147:19

^aDeut 33:3, 4

^bMal 4:4

Psalm 147:20

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aDeut 4:7, 8, 32-34; Rom 3:1, 2

^bPs 79:6; Jer 10:25

Targum

Psa. 147:1 Hallelujah! For it is good to make music in the presence of our God, for it is pleasant, praise is comely. ² The LORD is the builder of Jerusalem, he will gather the exiles of Jerusalem. ³ Who heals the broken hearted, and applies bandages to their hurts. ⁴ He numbers the sum of the stars, calling them all by name. ⁵ Great is our lord and abundant in power; there is no sum of his intelligence. ⁶ The LORD supports the meek, he humbles the wicked to the ground. ⁷ Sing praise in the presence of the LORD with thanksgiving; make music in the presence of our God with the harp. ⁸ Who covers the heavens with clouds, who prepares rain for the earth, who makes grass grow on the mountains. ⁹ He gives to the beast its food, to the young of the raven that cry out. ¹⁰ He will not desire the strength of those who ride on horses; he will take no pleasure in the thighs of swift men. ¹¹ The LORD takes pleasure in those that fear him, who wait long for his goodness. ¹² Praise, O Jerusalem, the LORD, praise your God, O Zion. ¹³ For he has strengthened the bars of your gates, he has blessed your sons in your midst. ¹⁴ Who has set peace at your border, he will satisfy you with the fat of wheat. ¹⁵ Who sends his word to the earth, with speed his speech will run. ¹⁶ Who gives snow as white as wool, he will scatter frost like ash. ¹⁷ Who casts his hail parceled out as crumbs; who is able to stand before his cold? ¹⁸ He will send the east wind of his wrath and melt them; he will make his wind blow [and] waters flow. ¹⁹ Who tells the words of Torah to Jacob, his statutes and judgments to Israel. ²⁰ He has not acted so with every people; he did not tell them his judgments. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was written during the rebuilding of Jerusalem after the Babylonian Exile. The Psalmist writes that the LORD is the builder of Jerusalem. The LORD will gather the outcasted Jews one day. At that time the people needed to praise the LORD and rejoice at the restoration of Israel. The city and Temple were far from complete when the Psalm was written.

Notes on this Psalm

This Psalm praised the LORD for the rebuilding of Jerusalem. What someone can learn spiritually from this time in history is that a person experiences a “dark night of the soul,” placing reliance in the LORD will allow the LORD to rebuild the person. No one is ever lost to the LORD. It is whether the person allows the LORD to take control for a while and help get the person back on track.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

